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Analysis of Drinking Water Quality Index of District Raebareli in Uttar Pradesh (India)

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Abstract

The availability of water both in terms of quality and quantity is essential for the very existence of mankind. In India, Most of the population are dependent on the surface water as the source of drinking water supply. There is heavy extraction of water for domestic, industrial and agricultural purposes lead to more than 50% of water wastage in the domestic, agriculture and industrial sector. Water pollution is rendering much of the available water unsafe for consumption. The lithological and geochemical makeup of the rocks, as well as different hydrodynamic parameters, all affect the natural groundwater quality. Water quality index (WQI) expressed overall water quality at a certain location and time, based on several water quality parameters. The calculation of Water Quality Index is done by using standard method given by Bureau of Indian Standard (BIS) and the World Health Organization (WHO). This research work is done by studying various selected ground water samples collected from ten bore wells of District Raebareli, Uttar Pradesh (India). After analysing samples different parameters are calculated such as pH, Total alkalinity, Fluoride, Chloride, Electrical Conductivity and compared with the standard value recommended by BIS and WHO.

Keywords

Water Quality Index, Physio-chemical Parameters, Water Pollution.

Introduction

Water is a vital component for human being survival and is an ingredient that all living organisms require. Water is necessary for all forms of life, either human beings or plants or animals and may be either surface water or ground water. But by increasing population of the countries and also industrializations, the water qualities are affected now a day. The polluted water is affecting the public health and aquatic ecosystems. Both the natural process and human activities influence the quality of surface and ground water resources.

Objective of study

The present research study is an attempt to analyze the drinking water quality of Raebareli district in Uttar Pradesh.

Review of Literature

The most important freshwater reservoirs on land are lakes and groundwater. These support aquatic life, particularly fish and are utilized for irrigation and home uses. On the other side, an expanding population needs a significant water supply. Municipal and industrial influence weathering erosion and other factors frequently contaminate water quality. Water quality can be assessed using chemical parameters with harmful limits for human health established at the national level. Health World Organization (WHO). Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality, the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) and the American Public Health Association (APHA) standards. These organizations provide guidelines, standards, and methods for testing various parameters like pH, TDS, hardness, microbial contamination. Basically the some parameters use to testing water quality like Fluoride, Chloride, TDS, pH, Alkalinity and Electric conductivity test.

Elevated fluoride level in the water can lead to fluorosis, a condition that affects teeth and bones. High chloride Levels in water can cause unpleasant taste, plumbing corrosion, and other issues. High TDS in water indicates a high concentration of dissolved minerals and salts, potentially causing issues like hard water, unpleasant taste and health concerns. These dissolved substances can include calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, and other ions, as well as metals and other impurities. Excessive alkalinity can lead to digestive issues and a bitter taste, while low alkalinity may cause corrosion in pipes and the leaching of harmful metals. Electrical conductivity (EC) in drinking water indicates the level of dissolved solids, which can impact water quality. High EC suggests a higher concentration of dissolved minerals and chemicals, potentially including harmful substances, and can reduce water purity. Lower EC conversely, might indicate a lack of essential minerals. EC is closely related to other water quality parameters like total dissolved solids (TDS), salinity, pH, EC also varies with temperature.

Methodology

Ground water Samples are collected from different bore wells located at different areas in district Raebareli, Uttar Pradesh. Detail of various parameters being analyzed using different instrumentation as; for pH (pH meter), electrical conductivity (electrical conductivity meter, Electrometric method), Turbidity in NTU (turbidity meter, Nephelometric method), fluoride (ion selective electrode method), Chloride (Argentometric method), Total Alkalinity (as calcium carbonate, titration method).

Result and Discussion

In present study 10 samples are collected from different location of District Raebareli for analyzing different water quality related parameters as below:-

pH Test

pH (potential of Hydrogen) is a scale of acidity from 0 to 14. It tells how acidic or alkaline a substance is. More acidic solution has lower pH. More alkaline solutions have higher pH. Substances that are not acidic or alkaline usually have a pH of 7.

Table-1. Analytical results of pH values of ground water from different locations

S.No	Location Area	BIS Standards (Desirable)	BIS Standards (Max.Permissible)	WHO standards	Result pH value
1.	Ghurhat (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.4
2.	Rahi (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.4
3.	Lalganj (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.2
4.	Harchandpur (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.3
5.	Ghorwara (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.4
6.	Salon (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	6.9
7.	Hittabh ka purwa (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.6
8.	Chedi ka purwa (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.3
9.	Dharai (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.6
10.	Churwa (Raebareli)	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.2	7.9

The pH value of most of the groundwater samples in the study area varies from 6.98- 7.65 and average is 7.6 (Table-1) which clearly shows that the ground water in the study area is alkaline in nature. Even though pH has no direct effect on human health, its higher range accelerates the scale formation in water heating apparatus. Distribution graph of pH for different locations is shown in Fig.1.

Alkalinity is the water's capacity to resist changes in pH that would make the water more acidic. Alkalinity refers to the capability of water to neutralize acid. Methyl Orange is frequently used as an indicator.

Table-2
Analytical Results of Alkalinity of Ground Water From Different Locations.

S.No	Location Area	BIS Standards (Desirable) mg/lit.	WHO standards mg/lit.	Result Alkalinity value mg/lit.
1.	Ghurhat (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	395.000
2.	Rahi (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	425.000
3.	Lalganj (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	545.000
4.	Harchandpur (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	500.000
5.	Ghorwara (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	370.000
6.	Salon (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	315.000
7.	Hitlabh ka purwa (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	290.000
8.	Chedi ka purwa (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	510.000
9.	Dharai (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	370.000
10.	Churwa (Raebareli)	200-600	200-600	320.000

Table 2 and Fig. 2 shows the value of alkalinity distribution which varies from 290-545 mg/lit. this clearly shows that the ground water in the study area is alkaline in nature.

Electrical Conductivity Test

The electrical conductivity is a measure to the capacity of water to control electrical current. It also depends on the water temperature, the higher the temperature will provide the higher electrical conductivity in the water. In Table 3 we provide our findings of different sample taken from different locations and their electrical conductivity.

Table-3
Analytical results of Electrical conductivity of ground water from different location

S. No.	Location Area	BIS Standard Permissible ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	WHO Standards ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	Result Values Of EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
1.	Ghurhat (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	94.740
2.	Rahi (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	106.300
3.	Lalganj (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	240.300
4.	Harchandpur (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	252.200
5.	Ghorwara (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	92.160
6.	Salon (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	75.440
7.	Hitlabh ka purwa (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	73.490
8.	Chedi ka purwa (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	163.500
9.	Dharai (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	84.630
10.	Churwa (Raebareli)	5500	200-800	71.450

Drinking water is prescribed as. 5500 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (BIS), 200- 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (WHO). Ours findings shows that Electrical conductivity of the groundwater is varying from 71.450 and 252.200 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. for different location areas (**Table-3 and Fig.3**).

Lower EC in the study area indicates the low level of salts in the ground water. The value of electrical conductivity may be an approximate index of the total content of dissolved substances in water. It depends upon Temperature, concentration and types of ions present.

Chloride Test

Chloride tests in water are used to measure the concentration of chloride ions in water samples. These tests are typically performed using methods like titrimetric analysis.

Table-4
Analytical results of Chloride values of ground water from different locations

S. No.	Location Area	BIS Standards (mg/l)	WHO Standard (mg/l)	Result value (mg/l)
1	Ghurhat (Raebareli)	250	200-300	27.50
2	Rahi (Raebareli)	250	200-300	30.00
3	Lalganj (Raebareli)	250	200-300	172.50
4	Harchandpur (Raebareli)	250	200-300	140.00
5	Ghorwara (Raebareli)	250	200-300	230.00
6	Salon (Raebareli)	250	200-300	32.500
7	Hitlabh ka purwa (Raebareli)	250	200-300	17.500
8	Chedi ka purwa (Raebareli)	250	200-300	122.500
9	Dharai (Raebareli)	250	200-300	12.500
10	Churwa (Raebareli)	250	200-300	12.500

Chloride in drinking water is generally not harmful, but high levels can affect taste and may indicate other potential contaminations. Present samples of drinking water have low level of chloride except Ghorwara sample (Table 4 and Fig.4).

Chloride in drinking water is generally not harmful, but high levels can affect taste and may indicate other potential contaminations. Present samples of drinking water have low level of chloride except Ghorwara sample (**Table 4 and Fig.4**).

Fluoride Test

A fluoride test can be used to measures the level of fluoride in water. Fluoride is a mineral essential for healthy teeth and bones and excessive exposure can have negative health effects.

Table-5
Analytical results of Fluoride concentration in ground water from different locations

S.No.	Location Area	BIS Standards (mg/Lit.)	WHO Standards (mg/Lit.)	Result value (mg/Lit.)
1	Ghurhat (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.62
2	Rahi (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.96
3	Lalganj (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.86
4	Harchandpur (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.61
5	Ghorwara (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	1.46
6	Salon (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.80
7	Hitlabh ka purwa (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.79
8	Chedi ka purwa (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	1.63
9	Dharai (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	1.93
10	Churwa (Raebareli)	1.0-1.5	1.5	0.64

The Fluoride bearing minerals, apatite, biotite, muscovite, hornblende, and fluorite, in the country rocks are the principal source of fluoride in the ground water. The application of agricultural fertilizers, phosphate variety, is the supplementary source of fluoride in the water. Consumption of fluoride contaminated groundwater (> 1.5mg/l) causes dental fluorosis and skeletal fluorosis. Maximum Fluoride concentration (1.93 mg/Lit.) is found in Dharai village in Raebareli (**Table 5 and Fig. 5**).

Conclusion

The result of the present study shows that groundwater quality and its suitability for drinking and purpose in some areas of district Raebareli is fit on the basis of BIS and WHO standards. The quality parameters of ground water in some areas indicate that the people in these areas are at risk of dental fluorosis, and skeletal fluorosis due to high fluoride concentration. It is recommended that ground water analysis should be carried out from time to time to monitor the rate and kind of contamination

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